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Aging and Institutional Care During Late Socialism: The Case of the Elderly People's Home in the Village of Pelishat, Bulgaria¹

Abstract: *This paper will discuss the problem of the institutionalization of care for the elderly during the period of late socialism in Bulgaria. I will examine a specific case – that of the Elderly People's Home in the village of Pelishat (Pleven Province), whose development follows the trajectory of displacement to spatial and social peripheries, typical of similar institutions. For this purpose, I will analyze a set of archival documents dating from the second half of the 1960s until the end of the 1980s. The analysis will take into account the socio-historical context of the practical and ideological role of (institutionalized) social care, as well as the government's attempts to deal with factors such as the (negative) demographic trends in the country at that time and the deepening discrepancies between the official image of universal modernization of Bulgarian society and the economics of shortage.*

The main focus of the text however, falls on the dynamic interplay of care and medicalization, and the ideological construction of the everyday life space of the residents who find themselves in a situation of shared accommodation (in dormitory), medical interventions and the auxiliary economy of the home. These aspects of life are usually normalized through categories such as "medical services", "culturtherapy", "personal hygiene", "living conditions", "labor activity" and others. The analysis of the ideological framing of institutional life can help trace the implicit and explicit discourses and set of disciplining techniques aimed at the facility residents and staff, as well as study the traces of successful adoption of or failure to follow the Party's official line.

Keywords: *ageing; nursing home; social services; institutional care; Late socialism.*

In recent years, research interest in the topic of aging and old age, both from contemporary and historical perspectives, has been increasing.

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This paper offers an examination of the problem of the institutionalization of care for the elderly during the period of late socialism in Bulgaria with an emphasis on the services provided by the so-called nursing homes. I will elaborate on a specific case – that of the Elderly People’s Home in the village of Pelishat (Pleven Province), which was intended for the group of “healthy” people of age. The home was located in a part of the country which had a high percentage of aging population, especially in the villages, as migration of the younger population towards the cities was significant – a phenomenon usually attributed to the accelerated industrialization of the latter. This situation, according to the local authorities, led to considerable differences both in the living conditions and the attitude towards old people in cities and in villages. It also led to the breakdown of family ties making traditional caregiving difficult, and with that – to more frequent demands for social and welfare services for the elderly and for the necessity of public response².

Why Late Socialism, Why Institutional Care for the Elderly: The Demographic Crisis and the Notion of the Caring State

There are several reasons for the choice of late socialism as a time frame for the analysis. Firstly, initial research on the development of such institutions in the first years after 1944 has already been carried out and published in previous studies, both in Bulgaria (cf. Popova 2001; 2003; 2019) and in other countries (see, for example, Brisku 2023). Secondly, the scope of the current text is limited to the amount and type of surviving archival materials on the case study, mostly spanning the period between the late 1960s and the late 1980s.

But most importantly, my interest is shaped by the trends in population aging in Europe at that time, against the background of a decline in birth rates and an increase in mortality rates in Bulgaria. These demographic shifts occurred against the backdrop of changes in the relationship between the individual, institutions, and the State (cf. Gramshammer-Hohl, Hergenröther 2021). The period of late socialism in Bulgaria presented interesting practical and ideological challenges for the State in this regard.

² Reports, information, questionnaires and references to the Minutes of the joint meeting of the Standing Committee on Social Policy at the Eighth National Assembly and the Presidium of the National Council of Fatherland Front, held on November 11th, 1982, on the participation of old people in Socialist construction and society’s care for them. Volume II, CSA, F. No. 117, Inv. 44, a. u. 524, pp. 107-108.

On the one hand, it had to deal with the aging ‘new man’ – men and women who had been socialized at the beginning of and during the regime, a population whose number had exponentially increased (see Koleva 2019). This shift brought about a re-framing of the category of the elderly – from being perceived as somewhat backward carriers of old values and traditions to becoming heroes, fighters, and builders of the new society. However, they simultaneously represented the impending demographic crisis in the country, and acted as a statistically observable reminder of it.

On the other hand, parallel to citizens’ life-course, the regime’s ideologically formed life-path was transitioning from revolutionary spontaneity to the establishment of a caring, humanitarian State (cf. Znepolski 2009). This transformation required the state to provide for its population, and this path became increasingly challenging due to the economic and institutional conditions of that time. As researchers have pointed out, the heteronomisation of the social milieu led by prioritization of the logic of the economic field on one hand (Deyanov 1992), and the overall interventionist manner of shaping everyday and private life on the other (Brunnbauer 2010), resulted in a peculiar deficiency of political power³.

As the sole official provider of social services, the State had to establish an adequate normative infrastructure for institutionalized types of care – medical, financial, and so on – that covered the entire life cycle of the New Socialist man in all its aspects. This endeavor required significant investment of financial resources, social energies, and ideological legitimation. In the spirit of so-called socialist humanism, which focuses on marginalized groups in society, turning them into objects of institutional visibility and tools for increasing the symbolic capital of the State, the question of the needs and problems of the aging Bulgarian population became a key issue.

Following initiatives addressing the problems of women and the handicapped, the Year of the Elderly People⁴ was put forward in 1982.

³ Deyanov for example, juxtaposes the over-bureaucratization of the governing apparatus with the development of the so-called *second networks*, while Brunnbauer describes a situation in which “The party-state asserts itself as omnipresent and omnipotent, it produces ideological guidelines for almost everything. However, it is obvious to all that many things are being done not in accordance with, but against, party directives, and any measure aimed at correcting these “deviations” leads to new unintended consequences that again require political intervention” (ibid, 189).

⁴ It is interesting to note that unlike ‘the Child’, ‘the Woman’, etc., ‘the Elderly People’ are (ideologically) constructed as a group, not as a single figure.

This interest coincided with the World Assembly on Ageing in Vienna, Austria, the result of which was the Vienna International Plan of Action on Ageing – the first international agreement on aging adopted by the United Nations.

Dimensions of Social Welfare and Geriatric⁵ Care: Institutions, Services, Socialist Ethics

The same year, in preparation for a joint discussion between the Standing Committee on Social Policy, the National Assembly of the Fatherland Front, the Central Council of the Bulgarian Trade Unions, the Central Committee of the Dimitrov Communist Youth Union, the Committee of the Bulgarian Women's Movement, and the Human Resource Reproduction Committee, a set of questionnaires⁶ regarding "some important issues of the elderly people in Bulgaria" were sent to members of the Standing Committee on Social Policy in every district and precinct. The document consisted of three sub-sections, each containing groups of thematic questions. The first sub-section introduces general matters and addresses 'the living conditions of old people in the city and in the countryside'. It includes main topics such as the attitudes towards elderly people in society and in their families, the education of the younger generation, as well as what kind of services are provided to elderly people and to what extent the mass media and community organizations address their issues. Other main topics included an inquiry into how many set-

⁵ It has to be noted that the term "geriatric" is used in singular occasions in the analyzed materials (cf. Ganev, Sabeva 1983: 164), and in this case it remains in the background of discussions on the care for the elderly. The few sporadic mentions focus rather on the necessity for better implementation of the findings of the field of gerontology and the overall geriatric medical services, with special focus on working pensioners. An example of that is a brief reference to the experimentation with "forms of specialized organization of the geriatric service" (ibid, 97) carried out by the Ministry for People's Health and Social Care. We find more information about this initiative in the pages of the journal "Sotsiyalno delo" [„Социално дело“]. The 1981 issue includes a long-standing discussion about the test establishment of separate geriatric service units [участъци] and their practicality. Although such initiatives are assessed as timely and well-intended, emphasis is placed on the organization of medical personnel and specialization in the field of gerontology. It is implied that there exists a discrepancy between research findings in gerontology as a scientific field and their actual implementation in medical practice – an issue deserving separate analytical attention. The cited journal reflects the then current social and health policies in the country and features numerous entries about model welfare institutions for the elderly people and in that respect also needs further investigation.

⁶ CSA, F. No. 117, Inv. 44, a. u. 524, pp. 24-27.

tlement systems the Home Social Patronage [домашен социален патронаж] service⁷ is available in, and the ratio between people already reached and those willing to use the service. Further questions explore whether the district provides day-care centers and clubs for pensioners, while their relatives are engaged in the “production process”; and whether there are any “prerequisites” for attracting old people who are still able to work with reduced work load in industries such as “trade and catering, local and cooperative industry, household services, agriculture, People’s councils, factories, enterprises, and organizations⁸”, as well as what their participation in the farming brigades is.

The second sub-section is focused specifically on the conditions of the nursing homes in the districts *relative to the set normative prescriptions*. The questions here address such issues as the capacity and location of the institutions, current numbers of residents, any waiting submissions and estimated acceptance time, as well as questions about the material base at the facility – building, premises, sectors, sanitary installation, garage, and so on, and about sanitary and hygienic conditions. Further questions relate to the quality of the provided medical care – staffing, quantity and quality of medical services, provision of medical care in and outside of the home, record keeping, and whether there are rehabilitation units and physiotherapy equipment, what the health status of the residents is, questions on the quality and quantity of nutrition and clothing provision, as well as the provision of any forms of culturtherapy, work/occupational therapy [трудотерапия]⁹ and any efforts towards their organization and implementation – whether there is a special sector, and an subsidiary plot [помощно стопанство], also whether the home has contemporary appliances and how they are maintained, whether a local

⁷ Also known as “domestic social patronage”, this is a set of individual medico-social services intended especially for lonely elderly persons and disabled people and delivered directly in their own homes. The practice was firstly established in the late ‘60s and included home visits by doctors and rehabilitators, delivery of medicine, food and supplies, house cleaning, etc. (see for example Hristov, 2022).

⁸ Ibid, pp. 24-25.

⁹ It has to be noted that in this form of therapy the emphasis is put not so much on the significance of one’s occupations with stimulating tasks, but rather on the type of tasks, which here are explicitly labor related: “The content of work assignments is selected depending on the characteristics of the disease or injury, the state of the functions to be restored, and the general condition of the patient. [It] uses various elementary types of labor movements carried out in the fresh air: cleaning the territory (yard, garden), digging and planting flowers, bushes, excavation work with a shovel, pitchfork, rake, etc.” (BSE Vol. 43 1956: 333)

organization or enterprise has provided a patronage support [патронаж]¹⁰ to the institution and what the connections with the local community and with the residents' relatives are.

The last set of questions is explicitly interested in the districts' organizational work and their engagement with the local authorities and public organizations. These questions seek information on the issues of the elderly and the state of the welfare services offered to them, which are discussed at the sessions of the Executive Committees (EC) of the People's Councils by districts and settlement systems, whether the latter have a long-term programme for the building of facilities for geriatric services in accordance with the Party's social and welfare policy, what percentage of 'beds' ensured by social services is, what social assistance funds are provided by the respected district, and if the one full-time associate position in the Sector Social Care at the Directorate of Public Health and Social Care is sufficient in terms of staff and what suggestions can be made in that regard, as well as questions about any involvement on the part of public organizations.

It seems that this three-step approach tries to cover and organize as many aspects of the lives of old people as possible (in and out of specialized institutions) and the social 'atmosphere' in which they find themselves in. This comprehensiveness of interest is based both on the explicit desire and need to "study" the overall situation of this "category" of people in the country and on the implicit interventionist approach of the State. The latter is tasked with taming, guiding, and being a guarantor of social relations. Simultaneously, it needs to offer official interpretations/narratives of their deviations, including those between generations.

In the narratives emerging throughout this document, several forms of *responsibilization* (cf. Foucault 2007) can be noted – the ethics of care as an overall societal and family duty, the ethics of care as a set of services and goods, and the ethics of care as a sign of political engagement. The questionnaire, on the one hand, aims to address the state of care for the elderly in need, and on the other hand, tackles demographic and economic issues concerning the potential inclusion of the healthy and able-bodied people in production and labor practices. The latter issue is included in all three sub-sections of the questionnaire, and later on was given much more weight in the procedural meeting of the Standing

¹⁰ A semi-institutionalized form of social solidarity – an affiliation between two organizations or individuals, the one usually providing sponsorship and support to the other.

Committee on Social Policy at the Eighth National Assembly and the Presidium of the National Assembly of the Fatherland Front conducted on November 11th, 1982 under the heading “The Participation of the Elderly in Socialist Construction and Society’s Care for Them”¹¹, as the title itself suggests.

In addition to that, the framing of the issue and the methods for obtaining and reporting data remain fairly standard, as they follow the set of question-points and key-phrases, that in themselves follow the pattern of the established normative documents and criteria that provided a legitimized format of (self)evaluation. This bureaucratic uniformity is simultaneously implicitly in-formed by the adoption of a levelling, sometimes concealing, institutional language used to describe and label the state of affairs at hand. Nevertheless, the materials received as a result are very interesting and important in both an informative and analytical sense. The preserved archives contain responses from the capital city Sofia and 19 of the Bulgaria’s 28 districts¹² as well as a single report from the city of Parvomay¹³.

“The Issues of the Elderly People”

Due to the limited scope of this paper, I will not engage in an extensive analysis of the sources’ content; however, I would like to sketch some of the key issues elaborated in and by these sources. Firstly, the attitude of the citizens towards the ageing population is usually described as *engaged, positive, proper, in accordance with the Party’s stance, no different than in the others districts*. Deviations in this regard are framed as individual exceptions and are rarely attributed to social changes, such as those propelled by urbanization and industrialization (as in the cases of Pleven and Kardzhali), or seen as a loss of filial duty (as reported for Gabrovo’s district, for example). The given response to the latter problems is universally pedagogical, focusing on strategies to discipline deviant behavior (through official institutional education, mass-media propa-

¹¹ Minutes of a joint meeting of the Standing Committee on Social Policy at the Eighth National Assembly and the Presidium of the National Council of Fatherland Front with attachments: exposition, decision, draft decision and report on the participation of the elderly in Socialist construction and society’s care for them. Volume I, CSA, F. no. 117, Inv. No. 44, a.u. 523.

¹² Gabrovo, Burgas, Targovishte, Vidin, Mihaylovgrad, Lovech, Yambol, Kardzhali, Shumen, Smolyan, Kyustendil, Tulbuhin, Pleven, Veliko Tarnovo, Vratsa, Blagoevgrad, Stara Zagora, Pazardzhik, and Varna.

¹³ CSA, F. no. 117, Inv. No. 44, a.u. 524.

ganda, public sanctions, etc.), rather than addressing the social and historical contexts that may have led to such behaviors.

The services of the Home Social Patronage – a relatively new practice at that time – were “well accepted and wanted” by the elderly population and, at the same time were seen as an economically sufficient option for the State. However, this initiative met a series of difficulties. There were normative restrictions, as the service was relatively limited and could be performed only in areas with a certain number of inhabitants. Consequently, in many smaller cities, villages, and mountain settlements where the demand for this form of welfare support was relatively high, the service could not be established. Additionally, there were practical limitations due to constant shortages of essential items and mobility infrastructure, such as cars for the transportation of staff and those being cared for or for the distribution of food and other goods, or the lack of a kitchen at the work-base of the social services, providing this type of welfare care.

The existence of day-care centers for the elderly was rather an exception, practically possible only in major cities (Sofia, Stara Zagora), and the establishment of small-sized ground floor dwellings for seniors in residential blocks, following the example of the GDR, was at an experimental stage. In this context, cultural retirement clubs were the most popular, common, and accessible social spaces for this section of the population¹⁴, both in the city and in the countryside, although there were additional restrictions for the establishment of these spaces in villages.

The spread of and conditions in nursing homes in the country were rather uneven, with intertwined discrepancies fluctuating primarily based on location – from the capital, through the large cities and district centers, to remote villages. Discrepancies also varied in terms of the homes’ age – from modern newly built facilities to repurposed nationalized old properties, and in terms of their scope and ‘type’ of residents – from fighters and heroes of socialist labor to ordinary citizens, and from healthy residents to those who are bedridden, or with severe physical or mental disabilities. In addition to that, many plans for new social nursing homes were postponed indefinitely, and the construction of those that had already started was suspended.

Public organizations commonly involved in activities aiding the elderly people were part of the local Fatherland Front, The Bulgarian Red Cross, The Bulgarian Women’s Movement, and The Dimitrov Com-

¹⁴ For more on this topic see Eftimova 2022.

munist Youth Union, as these were seen as having mediating, exemplary, and interpellational functions.

Last but not least, nearly all of the analyzed reports, except for one (Letnitsa), concluded that the full-time employment of one social worker in welfare establishments, as mandated by the state, was insufficient. This normative limitation is especially indicative for the social policy of the state given that the profession is framed by the latter as an “indispensable partner” to medical care providers in the field of geriatrics. Additionally, the appointed social worker had to be a trained professional, and often this was not the case, as many of those assigned to the position were employees in other fields and combined these activities with other duties.

The Case of the Elderly People’s Home in the Village of Pelishat, Bulgaria

The institutional biography of The Elderly People’s Home in the village of Pelishat follows the common early trajectory of displacement to spatial and social peripheries, typical of such kinds of social establishments. Although the records kept in the State Archives in Pleven are relatively few (there are no documents kept from the opening of the institution at this location in 1953 up until 1967), drawing from additional data can help to better understand the normative set up and the living conditions that such institutions and their inhabitants found themselves in. Studying the history of the Home gives us an opportunity to observe these institutions’ continuities and discontinuities as they embody the political, demographic, and social shifts in the country. For this reason, I will begin by sketching the prehistory and the early years of the Home, then I will continue with the second half of the regime (approximately concurring with the periodization of the Late socialism). As the last preserved materials are from the years 1989 – 1990, though it is not explicitly stated, we can assume that the institution ceased to exist not long after the fall of the regime in Bulgaria. The lack of documentation from the first decade of the establishment of the home, in contrast with the rich funds of its local predecessors dating between 1938 and 1949, is indicative. In addition, the available sources studied here are primarily of administrative nature¹⁵ – an aspect that requires double caution, considering

¹⁵ Unfortunately, the kept records do not include detailed information about the social status and biographical background of the occupants.

the normative and ideological language that permeates administrative documents.

Early Years

The institution is the successor of the home for the elderly [старопиталище] in Pleven named after its benefactor and local philanthropist Dimitar Konstantinov. The latter was established on the 9th of April 1940 with funds provided by a local board of trustees (called ephorate [ефория]), which had the status of a foundation and also bore Konstantinov's name. The initiative was run by the "Public Support" Union which covered and coordinated the activities of the organizations that were aimed at adults (over 18 years old) in need¹⁶.

To provide assets for the construction of the home, Konstantinov donated a three-story building to the "St. Nikolay" Church. The collected rents from this building were to be kept in the board's fund and used exclusively for this initiative. The initial donation was made in 1914, however, the actual architectural plans for the home's building were made in 1936, when the collected for that purpose sum exceeded the needed amount of 120 000 levs. Although the establishment was firstly envisioned as a joint orphan and poor elderly shelter [сирото-старопиталище], this idea was later changed as the cohabitation between children and old people was considered as inconvenient (cf. Balabanova 2022: 58).

At the beginning the home accommodated 17 people, referred to as *inmates* [нумомци] – nine men and eight women, and in the following years – up to 48 residents, though its capacity was 120. The building's style was of a traditional Bulgarian house "with wooden eaves, sheds and balconies. Large quantities of ornamental shrubs, trees and flowers were planted around it. This is how a beautiful park was created for elderly residents to walk in (...) To feed the elderly, an agricultural property/area was maintained, and those among them who had the ability worked. At the front of the Home, there were 18 acres of fields that were sown with barley, corn, beans, and vegetables. Pigs were also raised." (ibid 58-59).

After the political changes of 1944 in Bulgaria, the financial maintenance of the institution became increasingly harder. In 1948, all

¹⁶ More details about the structure and the activities of the Union can be found in its newsletter *Izvestiya na Sayuza "Obshtestvena Podkrepa"* [Известия на Съюза „Обществена подкрепа“]. During its years of existence, the newsletter also published few materials dedicated to this particular home.

charitable foundations and societies were liquidated by the State, and their funds were incorporated into the state budget. However, the resources provided by the state budget were rather deficient. Before that, the institution depended on the board of trustees, the Public Welfare Services, the residents which received pensions, as well as on rents and donations from the citizens¹⁷. In 1945 part of the building was rented out to the State Militia School in Pleven, which according to the available records did not pay its rent, while its pupils caused material damages and disciplinary troubles to the administrative body of the Home (cf. Popova 2019: 48).

The board of trustees is dismantled after 1948, and the home is re-named as “Dr. Peyu Beshev” Dormitory for the Elderly¹⁸ and later moved to other parts of the city (cf. Balabanova 2022: 59-60)¹⁹. This trajectory of *symbolic* and *spatial* re-shaping of the institutions for social care in the first decade of socialism in Bulgaria is quite typical. The act of acquisition of the institution by the State as the only legitimate provider of care is performatively established with the name change – a common practice when political and cultural regimes change, also used here as a way of ideologically “taming” the institutional structure which exist-

¹⁷ Nevertheless, tension between the charitable organizations in the country and the Bulgarian government was present even a decade before the establishment of the regime. The active participants in these initiatives saw the 1934's Decree on Public Assistance that put the organization of these activities under the trust of the municipalities, as significantly restrictive for the conduct of their work and for their financial maintenance, and as downgrading charity from public moral duty to a matter of state administration. For more detailed analysis of that period and the early stage of the Socialist regime in Bulgaria see Popova, 2019.

¹⁸ According to the archive funds in SA – Pleven the institution is annotated under this name between 1944 and 1949, cf. F. No. 469.

¹⁹ As stated in the description of the archival fund No. 89K: “with Protocol No. 60 of 22 Dec. 1952 (Resolution No. 409) of the Executive Committee (EC) of the District People's Council of the Working People's Deputies (DPC of WPD) - the city of Pleven proposed to the Ministry for People's Health and Social Care the Home for Healthy Old People to move to the village (present-day city) of Gorna Mitropolia, Plevensko – in the building of the Slovak School (fund no. 177, inv. no. 1, a. u. 18, p. 109). This probably did not happen, because in 1953 the building of the Dormitory for healthy old people was given to the construction workers building the power plant (fund No. 558, inv. No. 1, a. u. 25, p. 162). With Protocol No. 20 of June 9, 1954 of the EC of the DPC of WPD (fund No. 177, inv. No. 1, a. u. 23) a decision was made regarding the former building of “Dimitar Konstantinov” Home for the Elderly situated under Skobelev Park. This building, which was owned by the Housing Fund (“Zhilfond”) company and managed by the Ministry of the Interior (MI) at the time, was designated as the District Tuberculosis Dispensary – Pleven.”

ed and functioned at that time. This act comes to “switch” its identity and local history, it also demonstrates the displacement of social capital embodied by the new patrons – the representatives of the new social order. As Popova states, “In June 1948, the campaign to rename the social homes began. The directive of the Ministry was for patrons of the homes to represent names of people’s fighters” (Popova 2019: 46). One of the suitable and proven figures was indeed Dr. Peyu Beshev – a notable member of the Bulgarian Social Democratic Workers’ Party (Narrow Socialists) who served as military doctor during the wars for national unification (1912-1918). He also participated in the revolutionary events in Russia. Although he was born in a village near Veliko Tarnovo, the last years before his untimely death in 1926 were spent in Pleven, where Beshev worked as a doctor and political agitator²⁰. His tragic demise in a house fire – a suspected political murder – and his occupation in the field of medical care, made him a suitable patron not only for the Home for the Elderly, but also for the Technical School for Nurses and the United Primary Hospital Clinic in the city of Pleven.

But, as noted before, in parallel with the reshaping of institutional identity and (local) heritage, there was also the spatial redrawing of symbolic maps as such institutions, along with their ‘inmates’, were typically moved to other buildings and/or other areas – usually a nearby village, which lacked suitable material base and staff, as most of the assigned buildings had to be repurposed. And according to Popova, the act of “[a]rbitrarily moving homes and displacing inmates disconnects them from the urban communities they are connected to, and renaming them disconnects them from local memory and their donation history” (Popova 2019: 48). This strategy is quite interesting as it illustrates the asymmetry between the ideological construction of (geriatric) social care provided by the State and its practical gestures – its new face is established in accordance with the Party’s vision, but at the same time it is spatially and symbolically marginalized, pushed back to the social peripheries.

The following year, a “Dimitrovska Smiyna” Dormitory for Orphans after Fascism and the Wars was installed at the location of the home for the elderly in Pleven, which later became a home for children and adolescents. This once again shows the prioritization of child care over geriatric care²¹. But the status of the building itself was not clear as

²⁰ Beshev, Peyu Dimitrov (1883-1926), SA – Pleven, F. No. 628K, inv. No. 1.

²¹ Especially with regard to the families to the fallen fighters against the old political establishment.

it belonged to the Church which refused to hand it over to the City Council of the Working People's Deputies [Градският народен съвет на депутатите на трудещите се] and the Housing Fund [Жилфонд] until as late as 1952²².

Settling in Pelishat

Finally on December 17th 1953 the home was once again moved, this time permanently, to the village of Pelishat, with the move solidified by the statement of the Executive Committee of the District Council of the Working People's Deputies²³: "The Home for old healthy people from the city of Pleven moved to a single-storied school building in the village of Pelishat, Pleven Province". According to Popova's finding there is a resolution (F. No. 49, Inv. No. 1, a. u. 4066, pp. 14-15), which indicates that "The home has been closed and its residents have been distributed to eleven homes around the country" (Popova, 2019: 48). This adds to the historical uncertainty of the facts around the institution and its succession. Yet, the final outcome is that the home in Pelishat practically replaced the one in Pleven and served as the only institution of its kind in the area until after the end of the Regime²⁴. However, documents do indicate plans for the establishment of other facilities at different times, such as in the cities of Levski, Nikopol, and Cherven Briag²⁵, as well as in the district's center²⁶.

Along with getting a new location the nursing home also received its final name – "Elderly People's Home" in the village of Pelishat, Pleven Province²⁷. This, again, is not uncommon and can be understood as a

²² See Encyclopedia "Beneficence", <https://daritelite.bg/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/Доклади-и-министерски-разпореждания-по-ликвидирането-на-благотворителните-фондове-и-фондации.pdf>, 24.03.2024

²³ [Изпълнителния комитет на Окръжен народен съвет на депутатите на трудещите се]. Protocol No. 31 of 21-22 Sept. 1954, F. No. 177, Inv. No. 1, a. u. 24, p. 29.

²⁴ Due to the continuous restructuring of Bulgaria's administrative subdivisions between 1944 and 1999, for a brief period of time (1947-1948) "Vasil Levski" Elderly People's Dormitory in Gabrovo was also considered to be part of the Pleven area. Brief research shows that in the area there were two other marginalized social homes – the infamous home for "mentally disabled women" in the village of Sanadinovo (cf. AI 2002), and a home for "imbecilic" boys in the village of Luybenovo (cf. Popova 2022).

²⁵ Report on the 20th year since the foundation of the home for elderly people in the village of Pelishat, Pleven district, SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1, a. u. 1, p. 3.

²⁶ CSA, F. No. 117, Inv. No. 44, a. u. 524, p. 113.

²⁷ Although the very attribute in the documentation found is not completely consistent – the most frequent label is 'Elderly People's Home', but we also have 'Dormitory for

secondary form of symbolic marginalization and formalization, as many of these institutions later did not include a patron in their names, but rather were identified via their location²⁸ or type: “In 1952, the institutions for old people, already finally nationalized, were categorized by an order of the Minister of Labor and Social Welfare Petar Kolarov. They are divided into homes for elderly with mental disabilities (Podgumer and Sevlievo), homes for elderly with severe physical disabilities (Asenovgrad, Provadiya, Kyustendil, Ruse, Stara Zagora), homes for the physically and mentally healthy (a total of 21 in the country) and homes for the disabled from the wars and the fight against fascism (Sofia and Bankiya). This categorization is preserved in the years to follow” (Popova 2019: 57-58).

As mentioned above, the home fell under this classification as an institution for physically and mentally healthy elderly people, although there is evidence that not all residents could be categorized as such. An account from 1972, for example, states that “[a]t the point of accommodation of the residents with us, oversights occur on the part of the Department so that persons unsuitable for the profile of the establishment are admitted, namely: mentally ill, disabled, bedridden patients and alcoholics, which hinders the maintenance of general hygiene and discipline in the home. Incomplete and pro forma medical certificates are being issued – with fictitious diagnoses, often issued even without [carrying out] a physical examination of the individual”²⁹.

The situation described above demonstrates not only the practical state of disorganization in following established procedures, but also underlines the overall shortage of relevant social institutions and services of

Elderly People’ (SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 2, a. u. No. 3), and in one occasion – ‘Dormitory for People of Advancing Age’ (SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 2, a. u. 2, p. 4). The latter is mentioned in the annual plan of the institution for 1979, sent to and approved by the DPC, but in all of the studied documents the shift from ‘home’ to ‘dormitory’ [пансион] is first noted starting from the same year, which may indicate some internal shift. However, since in the SA – Pleven the fund is labeled as ‘Elderly People’s Home’ I will adhere to the same label. Usually the category ‘dormitory’ is used for the establishments that provided services entirely paid by the residents or by their relatives.

²⁸ The two homes for the elderly in Blagoevgrad for example were listed as Dormitory for Elderly People No. 1 and No. 2 [Пансион за възрастни лица № 1 и № 2 (ПВЛ №1 и ПВЛ №2)].

²⁹ Report on the annual activity of the professional organization at a home for elderly people in the village of Pelishat, Pleven district for 1972, SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1, a. u. 15, p. 4.

this kind in the region. This was a problem also in the decade after, as the capacity of the home was not enough to cover the needs of the district of Pleven, where the relative share of old people in the population was higher – between 20,0 and 23,9 % (Ganev, Sabeva 1983: 18).

The home was accommodated in the building of an old school, previously used by the local labor-cooperative farm [TK3C] for storing cotton³⁰. The conditions in the facility were not appropriate for the needs of an institution of this kind, which led to a long process of re-adjustments and modifications.

The earliest accessible document regarding the institution is from 1967 and consists of a report-note from an inspection carried out by the local public health and social welfare group at the State Control Inspection as it is one of the few narrative materials that are not composed by the institution itself. The general state of the Home is described as “satisfactory”, because it manages to provide beds for all of the occupants, and food within the established ration [оклад]. This, however, is seen as insufficient, and the head of the inspection group Ts. Dorovski describes the home’s conditions as akin “a barrack”. According to him the many “irregularities” [неуредици] “put the Elderly people’s home under criticism and damage the prestige of the people’s power in the county. For example, several old people were found bedridden in the common sleeping quarters, where 13-14 people are accommodated. They cannot take care of themselves, and one of them in particular cries like a child, because he cannot control his bladder and bowels, for which the others constantly berate and resent him”³¹. This particular fragment is very indicative of the poor and even degrading conditions to which the residents were subjected at that time, but also demonstrates that an emphasis was put not on their physical and mental health or the professional hazards they presented, but instead on the image of the authorities and their symbolic capital at stake.

Living Conditions

In the 1950’s, during its first years of operation, the home did not have indoor bathrooms, restrooms, and storage, and the latter had to be rented which turned it into an additional expense. The facility also lacked

³⁰ SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1, a. u. 1, p. 2

³¹ Report-note from the State Control Inspection for an inspection carried out in the Home for elderly people in the village of Pelishat and a decision on the result of the inspection, SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1, a. u. 3, p. 1.

an isolation room and a work/occupational therapy sector, and due to limited space one and the same room was used as a medical reception room and sickbay by the nurse³², as well as a bathroom and laundry room by the sanitarians, and as an office by the administrative personnel. The 1976 report mentioned above notes that although the local Public Health and Social Welfare department proposed on several occasions to the Executive Committee (EC) the need for funding for repair and construction work in the home, these were declined. This led to the decision once again to suggest to the EC the planning, funding and construction of an additional building that would provide the much-needed space or, if this is not possible, “a bigger and more comfortable unoccupied school in the district”³³. The severity of the situation was so great that the initial report suggests that the issue had to be solved with “priority, even though we are talking about old people who are living the last days of their lives”³⁴. This is a stance that illustrates the ambivalent position towards ageing and geriatric care which puts at odds the practical investments and the direction of social energies towards other groups which are considered more relevant (children for example), and the moral and ethical question of human dignity (and the Party’s humanistic programme).

In its first years, the home maintained three sleeping quarters with a total of 40 beds. The other available room was used as a dining room that was too small, which forced the residents to dine in two shifts. The staff, on the other hand, consisted of 5 people, including a manager, a cook, a servant, a washerwoman, and a drayman, with no medical personnel in full-time positions. In the following years, the number of personnel expanded, including a barber. Around the mid-1970s, in accordance with state norms, full-time medical professionals were introduced, amounting to 0.25 FTE (full-time equivalent) shared by several doctors, and 2 to 3 nurses. Later on, the list also included a shopkeeper and a supplier.

It was not until almost ten years after the opening of the home that improvements started. In 1962 and 1963 a toilet, a bathroom, and a laundry room were added to the main building. In addition, a farm building – part of the auxiliary economy of the home, and storage units were built in 1965 and 1966. The latter were remodeled as living quarters and isolators

³² There isn’t any data provided regarding the types and the quality of the medical services.

³³ SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1. a. u. 3, p. 5.

³⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 3, a line that wasn’t included in the resolution prepared by the SCI.

for the bedridden, and the main construction work was carried out by the residents and the staff.

In 1973, it was reported that the establishment was provided with home appliances such as a washing machine, dryer, and a heater, but they were not usable as the electrical installation in the building was not connected to the general three-phase electric power system – a continuous problem that made everyday tasks even more challenging. This was a significant issue, as all the clothes, underwear and sleepwear of the occupants had to be handwashed by two washerwomen, who had to be helped by a few of the female residents, as there was otherwise “a real danger that the residents will not change their clothes for 15-20 days”³⁵ and a possibility that the establishment would be left without even this staff due to unfavorable working conditions. Later on (at least from 1981) the underwear of the residents was sent to dry cleaning.

Similarly, the repurposed premises did not provide enough room and adequate conditions for the usage of more modern equipment that would ease the work of the staff, and the limited living space narrowed down the possibilities for leisure and culture activities for the residents. An illustration of that is the excitement and pride with which the new, rather basic, acquisitions that would make the environment more home-like, are listed and described: “The canteen, although small in size, was furnished with getinax tables, suitable chairs, tablecloths, hangers, etc. Individual dining trays were introduced for feeding the bedridden patients. Meals are given according to a previously prepared weekly menu. Having a vehicle makes it possible to supply the establishment with a wider assortment of food items to diversify the weekly menu. The bedrooms were given a more welcoming and hygienic look. The latter were covered with flooring, flowers were planted. Beautiful path carpets were placed in the bedrooms and corridors”³⁶.

These improvements were also related to the building of a second facility in 1972 and 1973 as per a later decision of the local EC. The expansion allowed for the set-up of separate offices for the medical and administration staff and other personnel. The preserved documentation indicates that there was also a workshop on the premises of the home.

³⁵ Report on the work at the Home for elderly people in the village of Pelishat, Pleven district during the year 1974, SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1. a. u. 2, p. 4.

³⁶ SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1. a. u. 1, p. 5.

The two main buildings, however, offered significantly different living conditions, even in the 1980s³⁷, as the new one was specifically planned and designed for the purposes of care provision. The old building had wider sleeping quarters with more beds than what was prescribed (as these were former classrooms), which hindered heating and hygiene maintenance efforts. There was also an adjusted kitchen with a dining area, bathroom, storage and a garage. In comparison, the two bedrooms in the new building had three beds each, new furnishing and separate restrooms. The medical practice was also located there, and in 1987 the setting up of a room for deceased residents was planned.

The possession of an automobile was essential, but the one available often could not be used as it constantly needed repair works, as evident in some of the reports: „The nutrition provision for the residents improved significantly, but there were times when the car was unable to run due to frequent repairs and it was not possible to deliver a wide range of food products. The weekly menu could not be regularly prepared and followed. At the moment the car is again not working, the availability of food items is decreasing and there is a serious danger of a decline in nutrition, especially with the impossibility of getting meat from the city of Pleven”³⁸. This passage – from a 1975 report on the home’s operations in the previous year – is particularly interesting not only because it illustrates the state of shortage, but also because it demonstrates practices of (self)censoring: the typed text is scribbled over and on the side margins of the sheet we find a handwritten “No” with an added line saying simply “*is satisfact[ory]. The resid. are on diets. Weekly menus are made regularly*”.

The question of the living conditions in the institution should be seen in the context of the overall living conditions that the Bulgarian population was facing during that period. And especially those of the elderly, living alone in remote areas of the country, as they were facing similar challenges, but often could not be covered by the set of regulations that the welfare institutions were obliged to follow. For example, data from a the 1982’s joint meeting shows that about two thirds of the elderly people in rural areas lived in separate households, and in 1975 the number of single-member households reached 163 000³⁹. According to

³⁷ CSA, F. No. 117, Inv. No. 44, a. u. 524, p. 110.

³⁸ SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1, a. u. 2, pp. 3-4.

³⁹ A main problem, along with the difficult material provision for the elderly population in these regions, is the problem of social isolation and loneliness.

published material, a “significant percentage of the elderly live in unhygienic housing, or lack some of the basic utilities necessary for independent living. Inconsistencies with hygiene requirements are present, especially in rural housing. Here in 38% of the cases there is no running water indoors, in 89% the toilets are outside the dwelling — circumstances that are a source of problems for the elderly in cases of illness or mobility restrictions. There are households consisting of elderly people, unfurnished with any of the basic items that alleviate housework. Moreover, these phenomena are twice as common in villages than in cities.” (Ganev, Sabeva, 1983: 40).

Medical Care

The renovations expanded the home’s capacity up to 80 people⁴⁰. Nevertheless, this number had to be reduced at some point as in 1982 the reported figure is 55⁴¹, although at that time the demand for the home’s services had increased significantly. This led to the number of resident admissions exceeding the planned norm on the one hand, and on the other hand, those with more severe impairments had to be certified by the Territorial Expert Medical Commission [TEJIK] in order to be more quickly allocated to other social institutions in the country⁴².

Medical services were provided by the doctor and middle-grade medical staff. They provided daily health monitoring and prophylactic exams, acute care if needed, as the residents were under a dispensary regime. Those who needed specialist medical care or were in need of hospitalization were sent to the relevant hospitals in the area. The admin-

⁴⁰ A preserved document from 1973 concerning the annual turnover of residents shows that 55 of the beds were planned for males, and 25 – for females, cf. SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1, a. u. 7, p. 2. This gender discrepancy is interesting as from a statistical point of view the ageing female population lived longer and was at a higher percentage than the male population (cf. Ganev, Sabeva 1983: 15-16). A brief line in an unrelated document (a report on the state of old people in the district Stara Zagora from 1982) might shed light on the subject. The text states that the services of the local canteens and public dining establishments are needed for the distribution of food for “the old people, and especially for the lonely elderly men” (cf. CSA, F. No. 117, Inv. No. 44, a. u. 524, p. 163). This may suggest that due to the common gender roles, ageing men could be perceived (and be socialized as) more unprepared of taking mundane but essential domestic care for themselves.

⁴¹ CSA, F. No. 117, Inv. No. 44, a. u. 524, p. 109.

⁴² Measures for the improvement of medical care in the Home for elderly people in the village of Pelishat, Plevan district, SA – Pleven, F. No. 983, Inv. No. 2, a. u. 3, p. 15.

istration of the home kept outpatient cards, and the facility had a pharmacy stocked with medication and dressing materials⁴³.

Campaigns to improve medical services also included a schedule for visits by the doctor twice a week (Tuesdays and Thursdays), scheduled measurement of blood pressure and urine sampling, anthropometric measurements of the residents twice a year⁴⁴, dietary nutrition prescribed by a doctor, regular sanitization of the equipment⁴⁵, as well as the preparation of annual discharge summaries. The residents' relatives had to be regularly informed about their medical condition via mail or telephone.

Regardless of the stated improvements with regard of in the medical services provided in the establishment, proper medical care was not necessarily always provided. For example, in a 1975 account we read that: "The service provided for the bedridden inhabitants is of an unsatisfactory level. The latter are not given help during meals, they are not given a daily morning toilette, and neither is such provided before meals. The bedridden patients are not bathed as regularly as the rest of the residents"⁴⁶.

One of the main criteria for the model geriatric care of the state, the provision of physiotherapy and rehabilitation *in situ*, was a long-term lacking from of service due to a number of complex obstacles. In 1973 this was because of the lack of three-phase electricity, then in 1978 such a room was established and a rehabilitator appointed, but this asset couldn't be properly exploited because of lack of equipment – an issue for which assistance had to be sought in 1981 from the Directorate of Public Health and Social Welfare⁴⁷. It was not until after 1982 that the documents indicate that the rehabilitation room was fully equipped, as is evident from the plans which state that the apparatus must be used to "its full capacity". The rehabilitation room had to most likely be used for

⁴³ This narrative description of the medical services provided by the elderly people's home is nearly identical with the reports given by/for other institutions of that time, as it follows the normative "check-list", provided by the State's authorities.

⁴⁴ Even this was an issue as in the plans, regarding the medical services of the Home the purchase of a medical scale was present from 1980 until 1982.

⁴⁵ Annual and quarterly plans for the work of the Home for the elderly people in the village of Pelishat, Pleven district (1978 - 1988), SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 2, a. u. 2. It is interesting to note that although the matter of hygiene and disinfection was a constant point the Home's plans from the late 1970s on, after 1981 the formulation "to be conducted mostly with sterile material" is included.

⁴⁶ SA – Pleven, F. No.893, Inv. No. 1. a. u. 2, p. 2.

⁴⁷ SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 2, a. u. 3, p. 13.

physiotherapy, remedial gymnastics, massage, paraffin treatment, radiation therapy, etc.

Among other duties, the rehabilitator had to organize morning exercises [утрешна ведрина] with some of the residents. It is interesting to note the discursive switch in the labeling of this group of exercising elderly people, as at times it is described as “the residents capable of work [трудоспособни]” and at other times as – “the healthy residents”, which indicates the implicit relationship of equivalence between *the ability to work* and *the state of health*.

Another gap in the medical services provided by the home was dental care, as there were no indications for a permanent appointment of a dental specialist, and the mandated prophylactic dental examinations were not being conducted by the regional health service⁴⁸.

Hygiene Habits as a Merit for Socialization. Social Work as a Vocation and the Limits of the Labor Discipline

As seen above, the hygiene conditions at the home and the personal hygiene of the residents are also a consistent matter of discussion. In his report on the twentieth anniversary from the home’s opening, the then-manager states that although general hygiene levels are fine – the residents bathe and change clothes weekly and at any time if needed, and the men shave twice a week – the overall good appearance of residents is in need of improvement and this is the duty of “part of the middle-grade medical staff and the sanitary staff. Residents should not enter the sleeping areas with shoes on and should not lie down with their outdoor wear on the bedspreads. A proper approach to the occupants must be found in order to break the old habits stuck in them before coming to the establishment, in order to accustom them to a communal life”⁴⁹. This is an example of the multilayered problems related to *socialization in old age*, which involve disciplinary techniques regarding the general, shared everyday regime of the residents, including policing their behavior as their dispositions are subject of re-education.

Here is one more example: „Many of the residents do not regularly do their morning toilette, and do not wash before meals. Individual towels are not used for wiping before meals. Toilette soap and handkerchiefs

⁴⁸ SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1, a. u. 2, p. 2.

⁴⁹ SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1, a. u. 1, p. 4.

are not regularly distributed to the residents, which also leads to poor personal hygiene in some of the them”⁵⁰.

The premises of the home were cleaned daily and weekly⁵¹, all of the residents were provided with individual soap, and from 1980 onward – with individual water cups⁵². In order to keep the sleeping quarters clean, they were allowed to lie in their beds only wearing pajamas, smoking in the corridors and living rooms was prohibited. The gaps in the occupants’ manners and those in the home’s supplies had to be compensated by the personnel’s strictness as they were the ones to instill good habits in the residents. Communal life, however, was not always helped by the staff:

“Meals are not aesthetically presented according to the guidelines of the Ministry. Desserts, especially in the evening, are served together on one plate /such as halva, olives, jam, baked macaroni, canned fish, pate, etc./ which often leads to misunderstandings and scandals on the part of the residents. There is a case of unequal distribution of food. Different portion sizes get served, excess portions are left, food from lunch is used for dinner for the kitchen staff, or food from today is kept for tomorrow, etc. Cases of non-use of given products for the day during food preparation, shortages of food items, etc. were noted by the manager.”⁵³

As Popova argues, after the establishment of the Regime in Bulgaria the replacement of voluntary work with paid labor did not lead to total professionalization in the field of social care, as this became an occupation with low income and low social prestige (Popova 2019: 59), especially for positions that did not carry high *symbolic capital* (cf. Kabakchieva 2016). Many of the mentioned reports filed in 1982 at the request of the Standing Committee on Social Policy show that while the normatively fixed number of full-time medical positions were usually secured, albeit not without issues – the demand for sanitarians and cooks, for example, was higher. There are records showing that in case of personnel shortage nurses had to be ‘diverted’ for the needs of kitchen staff⁵⁴ – a

⁵⁰ SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1, a. u. 2, p. 2.

⁵¹ That consisted of patting mattresses and blankets, changing sheets, disinfecting surfaces.

⁵² SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 2, a. u. 3, p. 7.

⁵³ SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1, a. u. 2, p. 4.

⁵⁴ CSA, F. No. 117, Inv. No. 44, a. u. 524, p. 13.

situation that would disrupt the overall operation of relevant social services⁵⁵.

As shown above, the other side of these everyday interrelations is the personnel, whose occupation held a specific ideological significance, as these people were the embodiment of the professionalism and care provided by the state. In this regard, if the figure of the aging occupant was emphasized, when highlighting their challenging behavior for the staff, then the workers at the institutions had to be presented as skilled and motivated men and women, providing a taming yet affectionate care: “People with hardened bad character and habits often end up here. They violate the rules of internal order and create a lot of trouble. And it is not at all easy to deal with the caprices of these people who have already set habits or [with the ones who] have reached dementia /complete forgetfulness/. We can imagine [with] what patience, what love the social worker’s heart must be “charged” in order to endure to the end. All the sanitarians are extremely attentive to the residents [...] Owing to their skill, these people manage to include even the most stubborn and bring them into the collective”⁵⁶.

But this position did not prevent them from getting sanctions – through administrative means or implicitly, by “creating an atmosphere of intolerance” and “implacable fight” – that came as a response to the possible damage done to the professional (ideologically pivotal) occupation as an *illusio* (Bourdieu) of the model worker. Such discrepancies expanded beyond the premises of the home and included lack of interest in participating in the agricultural work of the village labor-cooperative farm, non-participation in the political life of the village, sloppy attitude towards workplace supplies such as clothes and protective equipment, as well as unsatisfactory levels of discipline demanded by the Professional Union’s Head with regard to its members, etc.⁵⁷.

Over time the quarterly annual plans of the home paid more and more attention to the matters of work discipline, the utilization of working hours, and the inclusion of communal activities – informational talks, celebration of national holidays and anniversaries and so on. In 1984 for example, on the occasion of the joint celebration of the anniversaries of the Socialist Revolution and of the establishments of both the District’s

⁵⁵ Last but not least, let’s not forget the gender aspect, which reduces the female medical professional back to the field of ‘domestic’ care.

⁵⁶ SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1. a. u. 15, p. 4.

⁵⁷ Ibid., pp. 6-9.

and of the local Party's organization, the staff participated in a "call-pledge" [призыв-обещание] for voluntary engagement with an extensive plan for repairs to the home⁵⁸.

Similarly, those of the occupants that contributed to the everyday working of the home were publicly credited as a model for others and even given small prizes. These contributions, however, were once again strongly normatively and ideologically framed and limited, as the residents should not override the duties assigned to the paid personnel: "There are cases when the residents were used to wash cutlery. It is not uncommon for the canteen to be cleaned by the occupants, although all three of the kitchen staff are on duty. Both working shifts, from noon to 2 p.m. and the evening ones, are not properly covered. Being late for work [in the morning] is tolerated, and so is leaving before the appointed working hours have finished in the evening"⁵⁹.

As we can see, such discrepancies were noted and sanctioned, but not merely through the frame of exploitation and harming those who should be cared for, but through that of work discipline, the damage to the reputation of the institution and of the providing state.

Leisure Time, Cultural Activities and Forms of Therapy

In the 1980s living rooms in both buildings were provided – this was a key space for carrying out the so called "culturtherapy" [культуртерапия] – a term that captures participation in cultural practices as a form of social engagement that has both medical and developmental therapeutic effects. These are exemplary for the form of *medicalization* of life that aligns, at first glance, rather everyday activities with the frame of explicitly planned and controlled forms of institutionalized caregiving. It is one that, it is safe to assume, had a pedagogical function in terms of *ideological interpellation* and the ostentatious display of care for the socialist person by the state. An illustration of that is the following brief statement: "to conduct activities with the residents, selecting literature to suit their capabilities and above all from [among the literature on] our heroic past"⁶⁰.

These activities involved both residents and staff, and included a wide range of events [мероприятия] – from indoor activities like thematic talks and lectures, to going to the theater or cinema, hiking and excur-

⁵⁸ SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 2, a. u. 2, p. 41.

⁵⁹ SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1, a. u. 2, p. 4.

⁶⁰ SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 2, a. u. 2, p. 6.

sions. But ultimately, they were practically dependent and usually restricted by the material base of the individual establishments.

According to the documents, this type of care, alongside with the other key mode of therapeutic activity – physical care (physical education [физкултура], sports and a form of work/occupational therapy [трудотерапия]), were framed through the notion of ‘Socialist Competition’ which social institutions entered on the occasion of the 30th anniversary of the Revolution. This was a significant obligation for the unprepared institutions, but at the same time the opportunity could be used as a way of obtaining more resources needed for the improvement of the homes’ living conditions, seeing as they had to readjust and improvise to ensure satisfactory results. At the same time, this helped the launch of planned mass cultural work in the establishment, as prior to that “the residents lived their boring daily lives and had almost no variety and entertainment”⁶¹.

From the preserved monthly and annual plans prepared by the management of the institution we catch a glimpse of these activities. They included varying forms of monthly culturtherapy such as: 1) different study groups [кръжоци] (literary, on new history of Bulgaria, on “actual issues”) up to 12 hours per month, 2) political education session once every 15 days, 3) 8 hours of singing and other activities such as playing musical instruments, 4) attending film screenings with a talk twice a month; 5) television and radio, 6) board games, 7) other activities by choice – knitting, stock-raising, 8) joint celebration of residents’ birthdays once a month, 9) monthly visits from and to other organizations – pioneers, patrons, 10) 15 hours dedicated to maintaining communication with residents’ relatives and friends, 11) 4 hours at the home’s liberally, if desired⁶².

The types of activities and the time spared for sports and other physical activities was less in comparison – they consisted of 1) 15 minutes of daily morning exercises [утринна ведрина] 2) one-hour walk (if the weather allowed), and 3) sports such as gymnastics, ninepins, and others of this kind⁶³. The persons in charge are usually the matron nurse or any of the other nurses, with the manager of the home taking care of the political education sessions and the organization of visits, as well as

⁶¹ SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1. a. u. 2, p. 5.

⁶² Monthly plan for conducting cultural therapy, physical education and sports at the home for elderly people in the village of Pelishat, Pleven district for January 1974, SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 1. a. u. 5, pp. 1-2.

⁶³ Ibid, p. 2.

choosing the radio and television programs, the cashier is responsible for the other domestic matters – farming, librarianship, etc.⁶⁴ Later on, some of these duties were transferred to the rehabilitator and the head of the Professional Union.

Although the occupants did not practice work/occupational therapy in the normative sense⁶⁵, as the home did not have such a unit, the few of them that still held “residual working capacity” [остатъчна трудо-способност]⁶⁶ participated in the auxiliary farm of the home⁶⁷ and in day-to-day work – gardening, cleaning, hygiene duties and so on, under the prescription and monitoring of a medical professional⁶⁸.

In the home’s monthly and annual plans, the two types of activities were usually combined. As the normative requirement (the inclusion of such sections in official documents and so on) for performing work/occupational therapy was a constant issue, this trope had to be practically flexibilized and adapted via a sense of a *double game* (Bourdieu) against the conditions at hand.

Narratives between Practical Conditions and Ideological (Dis)placements

It is worth noting that 1982 was indeed the first year when the home’s management intended “studying the opinion of the residents in order to improve the quality and culture [practices] of medical care”⁶⁹.

⁶⁴ Typically, these positions had an underlying gender-based differentiation as the non-expert tasks, such as knitting, were entrusted to the female staff (nurses), while the male personnel observed and organized the more physically challenging activities such as stock-raising. The same logic can be traced back in regard to the occupants.

⁶⁵ CSA, F. No. 117, Inv. No. 44, a. u. 524, p. 112.

⁶⁶ This term was used to categorize retirees/elderly people who were considered as still able to work in certain industries, and thus were ideologically framed as a potential workforce.

⁶⁷ For this they had to even receive work clothes. For a more detailed description of the overall agricultural and animal breeding work, carried out in the home between 1978 and 1988 see SA – Pleven, F. No. 983, Inv. No. 2, a. u. 2.

⁶⁸ Although the maintaining of properties for farming in the nursing homes was established before the Regime, with the inmates’ work acting as a revenue stream and as a way to keep them occupied, during the period in question these practices were explicitly framed by a medicalizing discourse.

⁶⁹ SA – Pleven, F. No. 893, Inv. No. 2, a. u. 3, p. 15. Right around that time the plans started to include the keyword “culture” (medical culture, nutrition culture, hygiene culture) – a tendency that most likely reflects the ‘pedagogical turn’ of the state towards ageing and the problem of the population’s (economically productive) longevity. In a similar vein, activities focused on combating the use of alcohol and smoking among

The analyzed documents show that although the institutional “bloom” [peak period] of the home could be placed around the mid and late 1970s, up until the start of the 1980s, with improved living conditions and more reliable medical services, this acceleration was rather relative and conditional. In contrast with the cited external inspection from 1967, the narrative report from 1982 mentioned above is quite positive.

At the same time, the available documentation of the home indicates that from the early 1980s on, the institution struggled with its day-to-day functioning and financial state. Plans from that period explicitly debate the need for resource savings and financial restrictions – restricted usage of fuel and oil, as well as of the use of electric power, calls not to stock up the medicine cabinets, etc.

The following excerpts illustrate the multifaceted ways via which the administration tried to sustain the functioning of the home and at the same time to respond to the overall economic restrictions applied by the state⁷⁰:

“[...] reduction of direct costs except for the costs of food, medical supplies and amortization [...] To implement strict control over the use of electricity. The lamps in the bedrooms of healthy residents should not be turned on at night, and illumination should be provided only in those rooms where there are sick people. In the corridor of the new building and the lobby of the old building, only one lamp should be left on and all the others should be turned off. In the kitchen, after preparing the food, the electric stove should be turned off immediately. [...] It is forbidden to make private phone calls from the Home’s phones, as well as to make business calls if the work can be done in another way [...] In order to save drinking water, watering the flower garden is prohibited. Do not allow water to leak due to technically defective faucets, showers and batteries. [...] To introduce a strict regime of savings on the consumption of bread. [...] The purchase of furniture items under any pretext is prohibited. To purchase only clothing and bedding, strictly following the instructions of who is entitled to clothing and who isn’t. [...] Do not allow the waste of money [spent] on pig raising [...] Do not appoint substitutes for those on paid leave”⁷¹.

residents and staff could be mentioned, as these were seen not only as hygiene and disciplinary issues but also as moral problems.

⁷⁰ Cf. Resolution No. 15 of the Central Committee of the BCP, from 15.05.1983, CSA, F. 136, Inv. No. 76, a. u. 15.

⁷¹ SA – Pleven, F. No. 898, Inv. No. 2, a. u. 3, pp. 18-19.

Conclusion

Even though the home could not be described as ‘model’ as its predecessor in Pleven, it was not in a state that required immediate intervention. And this, in my opinion, made it quite ‘invisible’ from a political and ideological point of view. It was not big, it was not in a central region of the country, it was not a product of the latter wave of newly built homes for the elderly in the big cities, but a result of the fairly unplanned, early social policy of the state⁷² and it had soon to be “superseded” by the same social service in Pleven.

As demonstrated by the reviewed materials, here the notion of *care* was framed by a list of services. This made the home’s institutional visibility legitimate by a set of practices and activities that *medicalized* and *normalized* the everyday life-space of the residents. The discourse of the welfare policy and care encouraged by the state was centered around meeting certain normative requirements – number of staff and medical professionals, types of medical services, therapeutic activities and hygiene standards, number of beds, equipment and appliances. Beyond these met (or unmet) criteria, the actual residents did not get much of a presence or voice of their own. The official reports *talked* about them – usually in a generalized or illustrative terms. Their circumstances were highlighted in order to make a point or give an example in the context of the given institution as an establishment that was standing on the margins between the ideological significance of its purpose and its real-life limitations.

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⁷² As stated, with a little dose of distancing, in the published report *Stareeneto i Starite Hora v Balgaria* [Стареенето и старите хора в България] “for many years social institutions were opened where vacant buildings were found” (Ganev, Sabeva 1983: 43).

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